

TABLE 2—LIGAND FIELD PARAMETERS OF THE COMPLEXES

Complex	10Dq (cm ⁻¹)	B (cm ⁻¹)	β	β° (%)	ν_2/ν_1	λ (cm ⁻¹)	ζ_{sd} (cm ⁻¹)	LFSE (kJ mole ⁻¹)
NiL ₄ Cl ₂	8696	896	0.870	13.00	1.597	-399.7	799.4	128.55
NiL ₄ (NCS) ₂	8700	900	0.874	12.60	1.598	-407.3	814.6	124.80
CoL ₂ Cl ₂	3960	585	0.600	40.00	1.40	-200.10	600.3	56.81
CoL ₂ (NCS) ₂	3995	582	0.60	40.00	1.40	-200.60	601.8	58.27
CoL ₄ Cl ₂	10400	862	0.88	12.00	2.08	—	—	99.46
CoL ₄ (NO ₂) ₂	9991	814	0.84	16.00	2.03	—	—	95.55
FeL ₄ Cl ₂	10869	—	—	—	—	—	—	51.97

band appeared at 10869 cm⁻¹ and may be assigned to the ⁶T_{2g} → ⁶E_g(D) transition characteristic of O_h stereochemistry around the metal ion⁷. Using these assignments, the various ligand field parameters were calculated^{7,8} and are listed in Table 2.

The ir spectra of all the complexes of the ligand (L) follow a general pattern and detailed discussion have been made. The compound containing a thio-

amide moiety (H-N-C=S) have been studied by several workers and it has been suggested that all such compounds give rise to four thioamide bands^{9,10} in their ir spectra. The four thioamide bands are observed in the present ligand (L) at 1540, 1250, 1020 and 775 cm⁻¹. The high frequency N-H absorption bands in the substituted thioureas are not shifted much to lower frequencies indicating that nitrogen to metal bond is absent¹¹. The bands at 3200, 1600 and 1086 cm⁻¹ are due to ν_{N-H} , δ_{NH} and $\rho_{r,NH}$ ¹² respectively. Lowering of the frequency of C-S stretching vibrations indicates¹³ a weakening of the C=S and the strengthening of the C-N bond. The band¹⁴ $\nu_{N-C-N}(B_1)$ at 1540 cm⁻¹ in the ligand (L) is shifted to higher frequency regions in the complexes due to coordination through sulphur. Further, the double bond character of C-N bond is increased and confirms the M-S bonding in the complexes. A reverse change observed in thioamide, ν_{NH} , δ_{NH} , and $\rho_{r(NH)}$ modes in the Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes as compared to those discussed above suggest metal nitrogen bonding¹⁵. In the ZnL₂(OAc)₂ complex, two sharp bands appeared at 1720 and 1390 cm⁻¹ which can be assigned to

$\nu_{as}(C \ll O)$, $\nu_s(C \ll O)$ vibrations¹⁶.

In the ir spectra of CoL₂(NCS)₂ and CdL₂(NCS)₂ complexes, the ν_{CN} band occur at 2085 and 2070 cm⁻¹ respectively indicating M-NCS bonding¹⁶.

The ir spectra of CoL₄(NO₂)₂ and ZnL₄(NO₂)₂ complexes show the characteristic nitrate bands¹⁷ at 1280 and 820 cm⁻¹, 1285 and 825 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned as $\nu_{(NO_2)}$ and $\delta_{(NO_2)}$ respectively.

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Synthesis and Characterization of Complexes of Copper(II), Nickel(II), Iron(III) and Oxovanadium(IV) with New Tetradentate Schiff base

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In this note we report the synthesis and characterization of the Cu(II), Ni(II), Fe(III) and VO(II) complexes of the Schiff base ligand derived from 4-benzoyl-1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one and ethylenediamine.

Experimental

All chemicals were of reagent grade. 4-Benzoyl-1-phenyl-3-methyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one was prepared using the literature method¹ and the desired Schiff base (m.p. 319°) was prepared by its direct condensation with ethylenediamine in alcohol. Metal nitrates were used in the preparation of Cu(II), Ni(II) and Fe(III) complexes. Vanadyl sulphate was used in the preparation of VO(II) complex.

All the complexes were prepared using the following general method. Stoichiometric quantities of reactants in ethanol-DMF were mixed with continuous stirring. The resulting solution was refluxed for an hour after addition of one gram of sodium acetate. The product thus obtained was filtered and washed with hot water, finally with a little ethanol and then dried in air.

All physicochemical measurements were carried out as described earlier².

Results and Discussion

Analytical data suggest 1:1 metal:ligand stoichiometry for the complexes. Low values of specific conductance of the complexes in ethanol indicate their non-electrolytic nature.

Ligand used in the present study can take the following tautomeric forms:

Infrared spectrum of the ligand shows broad band in the region 2700-3100 cm^{-1} which may be due to ν_{OH} . This suggests the presence of structure II at least in the solid state. The free ν_{OH} is generally found between 3650-3500 cm^{-1} . The observed low value of ν_{OH} suggests the presence of intermolecular or intramolecular hydrogen bonding

in the ligand. The absence of ν_{OH} in the complexes suggests the removal of hydroxy proton on complexation. The ligand spectrum shows bands at 1630, 1597 and 1550 cm^{-1} which may be very safely assigned to $\nu_{C=O}$, $\nu_{C=N}$ (ring) and $\nu_{C=N}$ (azomethine) respectively^{4,5}. On complexation, the first and the last show downward shift, indicating oxygen and nitrogen (of azomethine) coordination. $\nu_{C=N}$ (ring) remains unchanged on complexation and hence coordination through ring nitrogen is ruled out. VO(II) complex shows band at 860 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to $\nu_{V=O}$. Low value of $\nu_{V=O}$ indicates the associated structure for the complex⁶. Presence of broad band centered at 3450 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of iron(III) complex suggests the presence of coordinated water in the complex. The complex shows split band at 1035 cm^{-1} which may be due to ν_s mode of coordinated NO_2^- group⁷.

The room temperature magnetic moment (2.03 B. M.) of the Cu(II) complex is consistent with the presence of one unpaired electron. The reflectance spectrum of Cu(II) complex shows band at 18,180 cm^{-1} and a shoulder at 15,380 cm^{-1} . The band at 18,180 cm^{-1} is presumably due to d-d transition in D_{4h} symmetry⁸. The shoulder at 15,380 cm^{-1} is in contrast to the spectra normally expected for planar structure (presence of such a band usually known as "dopple band"⁹). Its pyridine spectrum shows the absence of band at 18,180 cm^{-1} but shows a strong and broad band at 16,390 cm^{-1} instead. This suggests the pyridine interaction and the square-planar stereochemistry of the complexes would have transformed to octahedral one.

Diamagnetic nature of the Ni(II) complex suggests its planar structure. Its diffuse reflectance spectrum shows two bands at 21,280 cm^{-1} and 16,390 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1E_g$ and $^1A_{1g} \rightarrow ^1B_{1g}$ transitions¹⁰ respectively.

Iron(III) complex shows room temperature magnetic moment of 1.87 B. M. which is in the range required for low-spin pseudo-octahedral structure¹¹. The diffuse reflectance spectrum shows bands at 12,820, 18,180, 21,740 and 23,810 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to $^4T_{2g} \rightarrow ^4T_{2g}$, $^4T_{2g}$, 4E_g and $^4T_{2g}$, $^4T_{1g}$ transitions respectively¹².

VO(II) complexes show spin-only magnetic moment (1.75 B. M.) at room temperature. Its diffuse spectrum shows bands at 14,930, 19,230 and 24,390 cm^{-1} . Its pyridine spectrum is found to be very similar, indicating no change of stereochemistry in the donor solvent. Therefore, the observed bands may correspond to the $b_2 \rightarrow e$ ($-3Ds + 5Dt$), $b_2 \rightarrow b_1(10Dq)$ and $b_2 \rightarrow a_1(10Dq - 4Ds + 5Dt)$ transitions¹³ respectively. Making use of the observed energies $Ds = -2,70 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $Dt = 1264 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ have been obtained. Using the above, the absolute parameters $DS = 20,090 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $DT = 17,130 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $DQ = 32,580 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ have been calculated with the help of NSH Hamiltonian

theory^{14,15}. The ratio DT/DQ (0.525) suggests appreciable distortion in the complex.

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Alkali-Metal Complexes : Acid Salt Complexes of Alkali-Metal Salts of 1-Nitroso-2-Naphthol and 8-Hydroxyquinoline with Oxygen Donor Ligands

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WE report the synthesis of some acid salt complexes of alkali cations of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol (1N2N) and 8-hydroxyquinoline (8HQ) with oxygen containing ligands e.g. salicylic acid (Sa1A), 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid (2H3NA) and acetyl salicylic acid (AcSa1A). The method of preparation was the same as mentioned earlier¹⁻³.

Results and Discussion

All the products are stable in air, sparingly soluble in most polar solvents but decompose in non-polar solvents. These brown/yellow adducts of alkali-metal salts of 1N2N/8HQ and Sa1A, AcSa1A or 2H3NA, when warmed with either benzene or chloroform deposit green/pale yellow powders. Analysis and ir spectrum show that the powders are the 1:1 products of 1N2N/8HQ. These organic solvents leach out Sa1A, AcSa1A and 2H3NA from the brown/yellow adducts and leave behind a 1:1 salt of 1N2N/8HQ, suggesting that 1N2N/8HQ is more strongly bonded to the metal.

The transition or decomposition temperatures of some complexes are much higher than that of the ligands but in a few cases no conclusion can be drawn. The analysis and physical properties are given in Table 1.

It was believed¹ that the *pK* value was the only factor for the synthesis of these acid salt complexes. We, however, find that the secondary ligands which have lower *pK* values than 1-nitroso-2-naphthol and 8-hydroxyquinoline also participate in adducts. Thus it is seen that 1N2N (*pK*=7.7) and 8HQ (*pK*=9.51), inspite of the higher *pK* values compared to Sa1A (*pK*=2.97), AcSa1A and 2H3NA (*pK*=4.5) form more stable salts⁴.

Infrared spectra : Measurements were made in Nujol mulls for all the complexes and ligands between 4000-650 cm^{-1} . The bands occurring in the region 3500-1500 cm^{-1} only are listed in Table 2.

The disappearance of the O-H band of the secondary ligand (or its shift by 100-150 cm^{-1}) and reappearance between 2600-1800 cm^{-1} suggest that there is strong hydrogen bonding; when the hydrogen bonding is weak, the bands appear above 2500 cm^{-1} and for strong hydrogen bonding, bands occur between 2200 cm^{-1} and 1800 cm^{-1} . Utilising the relationship given by Lord and Merryfield⁵, the hydrogen bonded oxygen-oxygen distance in these complexes have been estimated to lie between 2.5-2.6 Å. These values, however, have only a comparative significance as many factors influence the oxygen-oxygen distance.

None of these acid salt complexes show anomalous and broad absorption bands between 700-1300 cm^{-1} . As such, acid salt structure with very short O...H...O (ca. 2.4 Å) is most improbable.

All the second ligands provide two binding sites for metal ions. The infrared spectra of the complexes suggest strong hydrogen bonding involving the —OH groups in most of the cases and the bands corresponding to the —COOH groups have been found to be metal sensitive.